

Wireless wearable wristband for continuous sweat pH monitoring

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Abstract

Several studies have shown that the determination of pH in sweat, which is one of the most accessible body fluids, can be an indicator of health and wellness, and even be used for potential disease diagnosis. On that basis, we present herein a wearable wristband for continuous and wireless monitoring of sweat pH with potential applications in the field of personal health assessment. The developed wristband consists of two main parts: a microfluidic cloth analytical device (μ CAD) to collect continuously the sweat from skin with a colour-based pH sensing area; and a readout and processing module with a digital color sensor to obtain the pH of sweat from the color changes in the μ CAD. In addition, the readout module includes a low-power Bluetooth interface to transmit the measurements in real-time to a custom-designed smartphone application. To allow continuous operation, an absorbent pad was included in the design to retire and store the sweat from the sensing area through a passive pump path. It was found that the Hue parameter (H) in the HSV color space can be related to the sweat pH and fitted to a Boltzmann equation ($R^2=0.997$). The range of use of the wristband device goes from 6 to 8, which includes the pH range of sweat, with a precision at different pH values from 3.6 to 6.0 %. Considering the typical human sweat rate, the absorbent pad allows continuous operation up to more than 1000 minutes.

Keywords: pH sensor; Sweat analysis; Microfluidic cloth analytical device (μ CAD); Wearable system; Wireless monitoring; Smartphone.

45 1. Introduction

46 Wearable technology has significantly evolved in the last years with the advent of
47 products such as smartwatches and wristbands. In particular, the use of wearables for
48 personal health assessment has fuelled the growth of these devices by enabling non-
49 invasive methods for continuous monitoring of physical activity and vital signs (An et al.,
50 2017; Jeong et al., 2019). Not surprisingly, the wearable fitness technology market was
51 valued at \$5.77 billion in 2016 and it is expected to be worth \$12.44 billion by 2022,
52 growing at an estimated compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.7% from 2016 to
53 2022 (MarketsandMarkets, 2016). Among the different physiological parameters of
54 interest, we must highlight the monitoring of heart rate (Chacon et al., 2018), blood
55 pressure (Boutry et al., 2019; Riaz et al., 2019), respiration rate (Güder et al., 2016), body
56 temperature (Manas et al., 2018) and sweat (Gao et al., 2016; Liu et al., 2016; Martín et
57 al., 2017; Nyein et al., 2018). In contrast with traditional health monitoring instruments,
58 wearable devices have some key advantages such as portability, ubiquity or ease of use,
59 and they are able to provide continuous, real-time, wireless monitoring of health
60 conditions in a non-invasive way (Gao et al., 2019; Ortega et al., 2019; Parrilla et al.,
61 2019; Xu et al., 2019).

62 Several studies have shown that analytes of interest in blood such as glucose, lactate,
63 urea or sodium, to name but a few, are also found in other biofluids sources such as saliva,
64 tears or sweat (Heikenfeld et al., 2019). The main advantage of using these alternative
65 biofluids lies in their easier access, thus avoiding the need for acquiring blood samples
66 and allowing peripheral biochemical monitoring (Chung et al., 2019; Zhao et al., 2020).
67 Sweat is particularly attractive since it is one of the most accessible body fluids, and it
68 can even be produced by on-demand stimulation using techniques such as iontophoresis
69 (Kim et al., 2018). pH determination in sweat is an indicator of health and wellness, and
70 it can be used even for potential disease diagnosis. Under normal conditions, the pH of
71 healthy human sweat is within the range from 4.5 to 7.0. Nevertheless, the pH of our
72 sweat can vary dramatically under circumstances of homeostasis dysregulation, disease,
73 acidosis and even stress (Perry, 2018). For instance, cystic fibrosis patients are reported
74 to have a higher pH (up to pH 9) than normal individuals (Nikolajek and Emrich, 1976),
75 and sweat pH can be also used as an indicator of metabolic alkalosis (Patterson et al.,
76 2002). In the field of sport and exercise, it is well known that the formation and
77 evaporation of sweat is the principal means of heat removal. If the sweat losses lead to a
78 body water deficit or hypohydration, the reduced volume of body fluids will contain a
79 greater concentration of sodium (Na^+) and potassium (K^+), which can cause hypertonic
80 hypovolemia (Sawka and Coyle, 1999). Severe dehydration can lead to headache,
81 vomiting, muscle cramping, dizziness, nausea and even fainting. In this context, sweat
82 pH can be used to monitor exercise intensity and dehydration since it is associated with
83 sodium concentration (Curto et al., 2012). On the other hand, excessive water intake can
84 cause hyponatremia, which refers to a low sodium concentration. Clinical features of
85 symptomatic hyponatremia include seizures, pulmonary edema, muscle fasciculation,
86 disorientation, mental confusion, respiratory arrest, weakness, nausea and even coma

87 (Noakes, 1992). Therefore, the reliable monitoring of sweat pH is crucial for health
88 assessment and wellness monitoring applications (Kaya et al., 2019).

89 Different approaches for wearable sweat pH monitoring can be found in the literature
90 over the last few years. According to their sensing strategy, a number of platforms draw
91 upon optical colorimetric detection (Bandodkar et al., 2019; He et al., 2019; Ahyeon Koh
92 et al., 2016; Lopez-Ruiz et al., 2014; Morris et al., 2009; Nyein et al., 2018), while others
93 make use of electrochemical pH sensors (Anastasova et al., 2016; Bandodkar et al., 2019;
94 Dang et al., 2018) reviewed by Chung et al. (Chung et al., 2019). In the first case, the use
95 of microfluidic devices allows the precise positioning of the reagents in a specific test
96 zone to which the sweat is guided, thus taking place the desired reaction with the
97 subsequent color change (Choi et al., 2018).

98 The study of the evolution on time of sweat both rate and composition in different
99 areas of the body has been approached in two main ways referred to passive sampling: *i*)
100 microchannel-based microfluidics that rely on deterministic capillary, the so-called
101 capillary microfluidic (Olanrewaju et al., 2018). In this case, epidermal microfluidic
102 systems that combine channels, valves, mixers, and reservoirs, are able to capture, route,
103 and store microliters of sweat in a time-controlled manner (Choi et al., 2018); or *ii*) porous
104 capillary microfluidics that rely on stochastic capillary flow within a network of pores
105 (paper, cloth, thread) in which the sweat is collected, and delivered to the sensing area
106 being removed by an adsorbent acting as a passive pump (Curto et al., 2012).

107 To make the system truly wearable and portable, a wireless interface is required to
108 transmit the measured data to the end user. Many systems include a radiofrequency
109 identification (RFID) solution, usually a Near Field Communication (NFC) link (Boada
110 et al., 2019; Dang et al., 2018; Ahyeon Koh et al., 2016). This approach allows the
111 development of passive systems by means of energy harvesting from the electromagnetic
112 field of an external reader, typically an NFC-enabled smartphone. Moreover, the NFC
113 antenna required for this design can be manufactured in flexible and conformable
114 substrates, even stretchable (Bandodkar et al., 2019; Dang et al., 2018). However, this
115 approach is not suitable for continuous, real-time sweat monitoring, since it requires that
116 the external reader is permanently placed close to the system. To overcome such
117 limitations, other systems employ longer range wireless technologies such as Wi-Fi
118 (Kansara et al., 2018; Lu et al., 2019) or Bluetooth (Alizadeh et al., 2018; Anastasova et
119 al., 2016; Nyein et al., 2018).

120 In this work, we present a wearable wristband for sweat pH monitoring. As Fig. 1
121 shows, the system comprises two main parts: *i*) a custom-designed microfluidic cloth
122 analytical device (μ CAD) to collect and store the sweat that includes a color-based pH
123 sensor built by immobilization of a vinyl sulfone acidochromic dye (**AD-VS**) on a cotton
124 cloth; and *ii*) a miniaturized readout module to obtain the pH measurements from the
125 sensor and extra circuitry to interface with the end user. The proposed wristband allows
126 continuous monitoring of sweat pH and real-time wireless transmission of the
127 measurements to a smartphone via Bluetooth.

128

Fig. 1. Exploded view of the wireless wearable wristband, consisting of the custom-designed μ CAD with a colorimetric pH sensor and a miniaturized readout module to obtain the pH information from the sensor. Real-time measurements of sweat pH are transmitted to the user smartphone via Bluetooth through a custom-developed app.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. μ CAD design and fabrication

Firstly, a piece of 13.8×17.4 cm² of cotton cloth, previously characterized by us in terms of Washburn constant (see Section S8), was screen-printed using a 43 lines·cm⁻¹ frame together with a black plastisol ink, to pattern 12 hydrophilic sections as shown in Fig. S8. Lately, the large piece of cotton cloth was cut to obtain each pattern independently, that will be used to prepare the μ CAD. Once the cotton patterned cut was obtained, the immobilization of the vinyl sulfone acidochromic dye **AD-VS-1** (Fig. 2(a)) was carried out following the procedure next described. Firstly, it was introduced in a Na₂CO₃ 10 mg·mL⁻¹ solution for 1 h to scour the screen-printed fabric and improve its capillary properties, as well as to get a basic media on the cloth that makes possible the click immobilization of the **AD-VS-1** via oxa-Michael addition by adding of 0.2 μ L of **AD-VS-1** 15 mg·mL⁻¹ in DMSO. Afterwards, the cloth was located in a light-safe and let dry for 24 h, and then washed to remove the excess of **AD-VS-1** by sonication in Tris buffer pH=9.2, purified water and methanol, 10 minutes each. Finally, the μ CAD was placed in the bottom of the designed holder and, on top of it, the U-shaped absorbent pad as shown in Fig. 2(b-c). The μ CAD, as well as the U-shaped absorbent pad, are disposable components that can be replaced when necessary. To collect the sweat, a piece of the sampling path passes through a hole at the bottom cover of the 3D-printed case, being in touch with the skin and collecting the sample while sweating.

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161 **Fig. 2.** (a) Chemical structure of **AD-VS-1**; (b) μ CAD design; (c) μ CAD photograph; (d) Block
 162 diagram of the processing electronics in the readout module; (e) Schematic diagram of the sensing
 163 procedure in which the LED and color sensor are placed in front of the sensing area of the μ CAD;
 164 (f) 3D views and real image of the fabricated module with its main components labelled.

165

166 In humans, the rate of sweating is around $1250 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ when exercising (Godek et
 167 al., 2008). For that reason, both the sampling and the sensing areas in the μ CAD design
 168 had to be small enough to avoid the need of high volumes of sample. On the other hand,
 169 however, the sensing area needed to have a minimum diameter of 3.6 mm so that the
 170 detector included in the device could perform reliable measurements. Cotton cloth was
 171 selected as the support for the μ CAD because it presents better properties than paper in
 172 terms of flexibility and bending resistance. However, as it occurs with paper, the cotton
 173 cloth needed to be patterned to achieve that the sample and reagent flow through a specific

174 path. For this reason, the designed pattern (Fig. 2) comprises of several parts: (i) a
175 sampling zone where the sweat is recollected or added, (ii) a sensing area where the **AD-**
176 **VS-1** is immobilized, and (iii) a passive pump path in which the sample flows to reach
177 (iv) an absorbent U-shaped material that makes it possible the use for a prolonged
178 operation.

179 Before the optimization of the μ CAD preparation, the analytical parameter used to
180 characterize the color change of the immobilized **AD-VS-1** was selected. For this
181 purpose, several small cotton pieces were prepared as described in Section S9 and tested
182 on pH solutions ranged from 4 to 9 (n=3), recording and analysing the color in the RGB
183 and HSV color spaces (See Fig. S13). The Hue (H) parameter showed a higher color
184 variation at lower pH with lower error bars reason by that was used for the study (See
185 Fig. S14).

186 Once H was selected as analytical parameter and the μ CAD was designed and
187 fabricated, different parameters related to the immobilization of the **AD-VS-1** were
188 studied. Firstly, the volume that must be added to the sensing area was evaluated in order
189 to cover the circle in a reproducible way. For this purpose, different volumes ranging
190 from 0.1 to 0.5 μ L of a Brilliant Blue solution ($10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were added, being 0.3 μ L
191 the volume that best and most homogeneously covered the sensing area (See Fig. S15).
192 Later, and based on the obtained results, the same test was performed using a $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$
193 **AD-VS-1** in DMSO solution to confirm these results. In this case, the volume that best
194 covered the sensing area was 0.2 μ L. The volume needed in this case was lower due to
195 the used solvent, since Brilliant Blue solution was solved in water, while **AD-VS** was in
196 DMSO and it affected to the wicking on cloth.

197 Later, the concentration of **AD-VS-1** solution in DMSO was optimized. For this
198 purpose, different **AD-VS-1** solutions from 1.5 to $20 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ (see Section S8) were
199 tested, resulting that $15 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ was the concentration that best results provided in terms
200 of CV as well as pH range of variation of the signal, being the one whose H value changed
201 at lower pH (see Section S7).

202 Finally, two different procedures to prepare the μ CAD were assayed. In the first
203 procedure, the cloth was first patterned and later the reagent was immobilized. In the
204 second procedure, these steps were followed in reverse order. The obtained results (see
205 Fig. S17) proved that the procedure providing best results in terms of reproducibility was
206 the patterning followed by the immobilization of the **AD-VS-1**.

207

208 **2.2. Readout and processing electronics**

209 The readout module comprises as main electronic components a low-power
210 microcontroller unit (MCU) model PIC12LF1822 (Microchip Technology Inc., Chandler,
211 Arizona, USA); a Bluetooth module Bluefruit Low Energy (BLE) UART Friend
212 (Adafruit, New York, USA); a high-resolution digital color detector model S11059-02DT
213 (Hamamatsu Photonics, Japan); a white excitation LED; and a rechargeable battery of 3.7
214 V and 150 mA·h capacity model JJR/C H36-004 (Goolsky, Singapore, Asia). Fig. 2(d)
215 shows the block diagram of the processing electronics.

216 The sensing module, which comprises of the excitation LED and the color detector,
217 is placed aligned in front of the pH-sensitive membrane, as shown in Fig. 2(e). The
218 selected color detector S11059-02DT is sensitive to red ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=615$ nm), green ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=530$
219 nm), blue ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=460$ nm), and near infrared ($\lambda_{\text{peak}}=855$ nm) incident radiation, codifying
220 it in four 16-bit digital words. These words are sent to the MCU by means of an I²C
221 interface for further processing. The excitation LED is synchronised with the reading
222 protocol of the color detector. The selected LED is white since the parameter to be
223 determined is the color of the sensitive membrane. After the processing, the MCU sends
224 the data to the Bluetooth module via Universal Asynchronous Receiver-Transmitter
225 (UART) protocol. The processed data is then wirelessly transmitted to a mobile phone
226 via Bluetooth. Fig. 2(f) shows the 3D views and real image of the fabricated readout
227 module.

228 A 3D-printed plastic case was designed and fabricated (see Fig. S9) to ensure the
229 correct alignment and positioning of the pH sensor with respect to the LED and color
230 detector, while providing a uniform dark environment for the color measurements. In
231 addition, to transmit the data in real-time from the wristband to the user, a custom-
232 designed Android™ application was developed. More detailed description and screen
233 captures of the application can be found in Section 6 of ESI.

234

235 **3. Results and Discussion**

236

237 ***3.1. Selection, synthesis and characterization of the acidochromic dye indicator AD-*** 238 ***VS-I***

239 Parallel advances in chemical sensing and wireless communication technologies have
240 sparked the development of wireless chemical sensors. In this work, our engineering
241 design is based on the use of μ CAD as an optical sensor for the detection and
242 determination of pH as the analyte. In this respect, acidochromism evolved for the sensing
243 area of the μ CAD by means of an immobilized acidochromic indicator dye as a
244 recognition element was thought to be an adequate methodology (Mohr et al., 2008).
245 Among the different suitable dyes, our selection was based in the appealing features of
246 vinyl sulfone azo dyes (**AD-VS**). These compounds combine the outstanding optical
247 properties of azo chromophores with the relatively high reactivity of the vinyl sulfone
248 group (VS) (López-Jaramillo et al., 2012; Morales-Sanfrutos et al., 2010). The reactivity
249 of the VS functional group fulfils most of the essential requirements needed for covalent
250 immobilization of the azo dye to cotton cloth as the support of choice for the μ CAD
251 fabrication: (i) a complementary reactivity with the intrinsic nucleophilic OH present in
252 cellulose that react by a Michael-type addition, (ii) a high stability of the resulting ether
253 link, (iii) it takes place in an aqueous milieu, and (iv) a simplified one-step procedure that
254 minimize the operational. On the base of these outstanding features **AD-VS** have found
255 application in textile chemistry (Mohr, 2018) and they also have demonstrated their value
256 in the fabrication of devices for optical pH-sensing (Chauhan et al., 2014; Kassal et al.,
257 2017; Mohr et al., 2008; Werner and Wolfbeis, 1993).

258 Considering the current state-of-the-art, we decided to prepare a novel member of this
259 family of compounds, named **AD-VS-1** (Fig. 2(a)), as suitable for our purposes. We
260 envisaged an easy strategy based in a straightforward two-step procedure that starts from
261 4-aminothiophenol (See Supporting Information). After treatment of this aromatic
262 compound with divinyl sulfone, that led exclusively to the corresponding thia-Michael
263 reaction addition intermediate due to the higher nucleophilicity of the sulfur atom
264 respecting to the amino group, concomitant diazotation reaction with 2,6-
265 dimethoxyphenol afforded the desired **AD-VS-1**. Spectroscopic characterization of this
266 indicator dye confirms this molecular structure which optical profile (absorbance spectra
267 and molar extinction coefficient in DMSO solution) was also determined.

268

269 **3.2. μ CAD and pH sensor performance**

270 As can be observed in Fig. 2(b-c), the hydrophilic section of the μ CAD is composed
271 by a sensing area and two paths: the sampling path (2.5 mm x 11.0 mm) and the passive
272 pump path (2.5 mm x 8.1 mm). A 2.5-mm wide path was selected since it was the
273 narrowest path that could be screen-printed on the cloth in the reproducible way. The
274 length of both paths, sensing area size, and position in the 22.8 mm x 32.4 mm piece of
275 cloth used to fabricate the μ CAD, were selected based on the PCB and 3D-printed plastic
276 case design.

277 After the μ CAD design and optimization, a calibration was conducted by dipping the
278 μ CAD in 10 different standard solutions with pH from 4 to 10 during 30 s in each solution.
279 Six different μ CAD were used for the calibration. In three of them, the calibration was
280 conducted by rising the pH value of the standard solution, while in the other three cases
281 the pH was diminished during the calibration. This strategy was chosen to prove that the
282 obtained H value was independent from the pH variation direction. As it can be observed
283 in Fig. S18 the obtained results were independent from the rising or diminishing of the
284 pH value, so the six replicates were used to obtain a Boltzmann equation fitting the data
285 set ($R^2=0.997$) (see Fig. S19).

286 The results of this first study indicate that the designed μ CAD can be used to
287 determine the pH of sweat with good precision and within the range of the sample.
288 However, at this stage it cannot be claimed yet that the μ CAD could be used for real-time
289 determination of pH sweat. The reason behind this is that the μ CAD hydrophilic area is
290 so small that it will be full of sample in a very short period of time. Because of that, some
291 material needed to be included for the purpose of continuously retiring sample from the
292 hydrophilic area of the μ CAD to allow that new sample could continue flowing through
293 it. This would ensure that the μ CAD could be used during longer periods of time before
294 saturating. The strategy followed was the inclusion of a passive pump in the μ CAD, along
295 with an absorbent pad containing Flexicel (P&G Spain, Madrid) skirting the hydrophilic
296 area (see Fig. 2(b-c)). Flexicel is a superabsorbent material that can absorb around 20
297 times its weight (see the slope of the calibration function in Fig. S20(a)). This material
298 has been successfully used as passive pump in other microfluidic devices that can be
299 found in the literature (Suarez et al., 2020). The area of the absorbent pad used in our

300 design was 689 mm². Based on the calibration of the material and considering a sweat
 301 rate of 0.01 μL·s⁻¹ (in around 15 mm² area) (Godek et al., 2008), the μCAD along with
 302 the absorbent pad could be used continuously up to 1058 min. Size and shape of the
 303 absorbent material was selected based in the 3D-printed plastic case, to be easy-to-place
 304 inside while maintaining its position inside along the use of the device.

305 A new calibration was conducted, on this occasion with the μCAD including the
 306 passive pump. In this case, a syringe pump was used to apply the sample on the sampling
 307 zone (see Fig. 2(b)) at a flow rate similar to the human sweat rate (0.01 μL·s⁻¹). Each pH
 308 standard solution was applied to the μCAD during two minutes and videotaped. From the
 309 obtained results (see Fig. S21) it can be observed that only 90 seconds were enough to
 310 get a steady signal, which was used to obtain the calibration function (see Fig. 3) The data
 311 fits as previously described to a Boltzmann equation (R²=0.996) (Eq. S2), and the range
 312 of use of the μCAD is from 6.1 to 8.4 (pKa=7.4), range in which the pH of sweat is
 313 included. The precision tested at different pH goes from 2.3 to 3.6 % (see Table 1).
 314

315
 316 **Fig. 3.** Calibration of the μCAD adding the standards solution using a syringe pump at a rate of
 317 0.01 μL·s⁻¹.
 318

319 **Table 1.** Analytical parameters of μCAD.

Analytical parameters			
A₁	0.104	Precision (n=10)	
A₂	0.047	pH	CV (%)
A₃	7.372		
A₄	0.614	4.04	2.5
R²	0.996	7.45	3.5
LOD	6.1	7.97	2.3
Range	6.1 - 8.4	9.97	3.6

330
 331

332 Due to the nature of the sweat sample, whose pH can rise or diminish indistinctly
333 during an exercise session, an additional study was conducted to prove that the μ CAD is
334 fully reversible to pH variations. Fig. S22 shows that the μ CADs are fully reversible after
335 subjecting them to a cycle of acidic-basic-acidic pH and basic-acidic-basic pH,
336 respectively. Finally, a stability study was performed by studying the H value of three
337 different μ CADs along 20 weeks. This study showed that, once prepared, the μ CAD can
338 be stored for 7 weeks (Fig. S23). Once the μ CAD was fully characterized, seven different
339 samples were analysed using the μ CAD and the obtained results were compared to the
340 ones provided by a pH-meter (Section S16).

341

342 ***3.3. Wristband performance and evaluation***

343

344 As indicated in the previous section, the μ CAD was analytically characterized for pH
345 sensing and a calibration function was obtained using a camera to register the color
346 variations (see Fig. 3). At this stage, the whole system was characterized using the
347 optimized μ CAD in combination with the readout and processing electronics. Thus, the
348 way of registering the color changes in the μ CAD due to the sweat pH was conducted
349 through the digital color sensor included in the readout circuit (see Fig. 4(a-b)). For the
350 calibration, a similar setup than the previous case was employed, i.e. a syringe pump was
351 used to apply the sample on the sampling zone at a flow rate similar to the human sweat
352 rate ($0.01 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). Each pH standard solution was applied to the μ CAD during two
353 minutes and the color measurements from the digital sensor were transmitted every
354 second to the smartphone app via Bluetooth. Fig. 4(c) shows the obtained calibration
355 curve, that can be again fitted to a Boltzmann curve ($R^2=0.997$) (Eq. S2). In this case, the
356 range of use of the μ CAD ranges from 6.0 to 8.0, and the precision at different pH values
357 goes from 3.6 to 6.0 % (see Table 2). In addition, the system was tested in real-life
358 conditions by wearing it on the wrist while exercising and transmitting the data in real-
359 time to a smartphone via Bluetooth. Fig. 4(d) shows the experimental setup and the
360 obtained results. It can be observed that during the first 10 min of physical activity the
361 low sweat rate is not enough to wet the cloth sensor. After that, the pH increases due to
362 the decrease of lactic acid in sweat.

363

364 **Fig. 4.** (a) Layer by layer top view of the wristband, including: 1) Low-Energy Bluetooth module,
 365 2) battery, 3) PCB, and 4) absorbent pad with μ CAD; (b) Bottom view of the wristband
 366 (uncovered) with and without the μ CAD layer to allow the view of the LED and color detector;
 367 (c) Calibration curve of the wristband wearable system in terms of H value; (d) Real-time results
 368 of the wearable system placed on the wristband during exercise.
 369
 370

371 **Table 2.** Analytical parameters of the wristband.

Analytical parameters			
A_1	0.210	Precision (n=10)	
A_2	0.050	pH	CV (%)
A_3	0.699	6.00	4.0
A_4	0.377	6.43	6.0
R^2	0.997	6.93	4.5
LOD	6.0	7.45	4.3
Range	6.0 - 8.0	7.97	3.6

383 Overall, the developed system is convenient in terms of portability, ease of use and
 384 wearability. A number of previous works have focused on the development of sensing
 385 patches for sweat pH monitoring (Curto et al., 2012; He et al., 2019; A. Koh et al., 2016;
 386 Morris et al., 2009; Zhao et al., 2020), but they lacked the associated readout and
 387 processing electronics to obtain and transmit in real-time the measured information to the
 388 end user. In contrast to the RFID/NFC-based platforms for pH sweat sensing than can be
 389 found in previous literature (Bandodkar et al., 2019; Boada et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2019),
 390 our proposed wristband does not require that the external reader is permanently placed in
 391 its close proximity, thus allowing a truly continuous real-time monitoring. In return, our
 392 system requires a battery for its operation, which is not needed in the case of RFID/NFC

393 devices with energy harvesting capabilities (Dang et al., 2018). However, the use of low-
394 power components in combination with the non-continuous measurement strategy allows
395 a long battery life of more than 2 days (see Section S14). In terms of response speed, our
396 system only takes 90 seconds to get a steady signal in the sensing zone through the use of
397 the passive pump to collect the sweat, which is significantly lower than the time required
398 in other systems to get the first readings (Liu et al., 2016). Besides, the proposed
399 wristband is distinguished from previous sweat pH monitoring systems in two more
400 aspects: firstly, it features a very compact design with a size similar to a wristwatch,
401 making it more comfortable to use than other devices that must be placed, for instance,
402 in the back; and secondly, it is completed by a custom-developed user-friendly
403 smartphone application (Alizadeh et al., 2018; Anastasova et al., 2017; Morris et al.,
404 2009; Nyein et al., 2018).

405

406 **4. Conclusions**

407 A wearable wristband for sweat pH wireless monitoring was developed combining a
408 custom-designed μ CAD and associated readout and processing electronics. The μ CAD
409 was designed in 100% cotton cloth by immobilizing an acidochromic dye (**AD-VS-1**).
410 The μ CAD consists of a sampling area to collect the sweat, a colorimetric sensing area, a
411 passive pump path, and an absorbent pad that allows continuous operation up to 100 min
412 if we consider a typical human sweat rate ($0.01 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). The H value in the HSV color
413 space was selected as the best parameter to correlate the color change in the sensing area
414 due to the pH variations. The readout module consists of a low-power microcontroller
415 unit that controls a white LED and a digital color sensor to detect the color variations in
416 the μ CAD sensing area. In addition, a Bluetooth module transmits in real-time the
417 measurements to a friendly-user smartphone application. The analytical characterization
418 of the μ CAD alone showed that the H parameter can be related to the sweat pH value and
419 fitted to a Boltzmann equation ($R^2=0.996$). The range of use of the μ CAD goes from 6.1
420 to 8.4, which includes the pH range of sweat. The precision tested at different pH values
421 goes from 2.3 to 3.6 %. When compared to a commercial pH-meter with different
422 samples, the error in the determination was around 2% in almost all the cases. The
423 analytical characterization of the wristband as a whole showed a good fitting ($R^2=0.997$
424 in the Boltzmann equation) with a range of use from 6 to 8 and a precision at different pH
425 values from 3.6 to 6.0 %. With an estimated battery life up to 2.63 days in non-continuous
426 sensing mode, the developed system has potential applications in the field of personal
427 health assessment.

428

429 **Declaration of interests**

430 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
431 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

432

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